

Perceptions Of Female Social Work Faculty Members On The Challenges Facing Family Counselling In Saudi Society

Khaloud Barjas Alabdulkareem

Article Info

Article History

Received:
May 15, 2021

Accepted:
October 19, 2021

Keywords :

Female Social Work,
Saudi Society,
qualification challenges,
family

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5579295

Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the challenges facing the profession of social work in the field of family counselling and therapy in the Saudi society based on the opinions of specialised academics in the departments of social work in Saudi universities. The challenges were categorised according to the following dimensions: qualification challenges, professional challenges and community challenges. The study focused on the family sphere because this is the aspect that is most affected by contemporary social changes.: The study revealed that social workers in the field of family counselling and therapy in Saudi society face numerous qualifications, professional and community challenges. It then provided a set of recommendations to address these challenges. Applications: The challenges facing social workers must be taken into consideration when practicing family counselling and therapy to understand what social workers are experiencing in order to find ways and solutions to address these difficulties.

Introduction

The Saudi society is witnessing a qualitative shift in various aspects of economic, cultural, social and occupational life. These shifts and changes, as confirmed by the systems theory (Hartman & Larid, 1983: 63), affect and are affected by each other and have direct and indirect effects on the family and marital systems. The resulting positive and negative changes, in turn, affect individuals and families. Owing to these contemporary changes and their accompanying problems, many governmental, private and non-profit entities have sought to establish family and marital counselling centres where family and marital social work are practiced.

Despite the importance and position of these institutions, most of them face extensive challenges or constraints because of recent the societal changes. Thus, social workers need to be aware of these challenges and take steps to avoid them in order to achieve the objectives of the counselling centres. Al-Saleh (2017); Al-Sharqawi and Al-Aweed (2015) indicated that many constraints in the Saudi society confront social work practitioners in their work which impede the use of appropriate professional methods.

Based on contemporary challenges facing family counselling institutions, the issue of women empowerment is particularly significant, especially with the rise of the development movement in the Kingdom. The Kingdom's Vision 2030 aims to increase women's empowerment, increase their contribution to various areas of development and expand their employment opportunities, in addition to developing the support services and facilities necessary to enable them to perform their roles. In accordance with Vision 2030, the state has introduced regulations and laws to enable women socially and economically. The most important of these efforts relate to ensuring women's civil rights, organising the work of women, and providing numerous laws and regulations, leading to many more opportunities for their involvement in the labour force in the government as well as in private and charitable sectors.

Accordingly, this study sought the views of academic officials in social work to determine their opinions about the future of the social work profession based on this new development in the roles of women in the Saudi society and the challenges and difficulties that arise as a consequence. Females are also more responsible and deeply affected by these challenges than males. One reason the researchers sought the views of female social work faculty members is because women have a better understanding of other women and are more aware of the changes and challenges affecting them. Therefore, the current study contributes to the literature on this topic by investigating the contemporary challenges social workers face in the field of family counselling and therapy in the Saudi society.

Given that most of the latest social, economic and legal changes happening in Saudi Society pertain to women, and since those changes would likely result in social, family and marital problems, discussing the subject from a female perspective seems more reasonable. Some of these views originate from feminist theories.

Feminist theory

1. Liberal feminist theory

Liberal feminism, one of the oldest feminist movements, started from the late 19th century to the beginning of the 20th century. It originally referred to the liberal philosophy founded by John Locke and Jean-Jacques Rousseau and was developed by Viet Nam and Mel according to the principles of democracy, freedom, justice and equality. In addressing the social inequalities faced by women, liberal theory criticises disparities based on the biological differences between men and women. The theory suggests that the differences between men and women are not significant, and thus, differences in their rights are created that perpetuate patterns of inequality that are unfair to women, compared to what men receive communally (Abdul Azim, 2014: 641).

Liberal theory refutes gender-based differences between men and women and confirms that promoting such differences is what produces social inequalities and influences societal acceptance. It rejects sexual differences between men and women and calls for the elimination of all forms of social discrimination between them, particularly in the fields of employment and education. According to liberal theory, it is unacceptable to justify differences between men and women on a biological basis and exploit these negative perceptions to perpetuate differences in the levels of employment, associated income inequality and access to higher positions (Alshehri, 2019: 49).

Liberal feminist theory has achieved many successes in supporting women to enter the labour market. However, it has been less successful in eliminating undeclared forms of discrimination in employment institutions that prevent women from making progress and rising to senior positions in line with men. Note that liberal feminism was the first and most important step towards achieving gender equality by drawing practical attention to the reality of the differences society imposes on women despite their efforts being equal to those of men (Abdul Azim, 2014: 641).

2. Marxist feminist theory

This theory focuses on the biological basis of human nature and suggests that the concept of class defines the nature, characteristics and roles of gender. Recent changes have perpetuated the role of women in having children while men take control of economic sources, making women dependent and subordinate. Women have accepted men's control to provide them with livelihood. In this regard, the Marxist feminist theory has attempted to change the circumstances facing women by changing the foundations of their exploitation. According to the opinions of Marxist feminism, women are prepared to assume the roles that society demands of them and Marxist feminism advocates the need to look at the nature of the work performed by women and their social relationships which forms their ideas and determines their consciousness. The woman suffers from alienation, works in childbearing, and serves her spouse. This confirms that the position of women will only improve if they can make personal achievements, perform work that is valued and beneficial to the society as a whole (Alnajem, 2012: 11).

3- Radical feminist theory:

The main objective of this theory is to change the society in which women exist in order to end their exploitation. Radical feminism reveals the sexual exploitation of women which supports the patriarchal dominance of men over women. This view believes that men are responsible for the exploitation of women through the patriarchal system in which men prevail over women (Abdul Azim, 2014: 645).

Although some of the feminist theories presented above were not agreed upon by anti-feminists, it can be said that the feminist perspective has helped to draw attention to women's issues and to advocate for empowering women and giving them more rights in the fields of employment and education.

Implementing a feminist perspective in explaining the problem of the current study:

Based on Vision 2030, Saudi Arabia has launched a great number of human rights and social initiatives that have contributed significantly to Saudi women's entry into the labour force. Social and human rights have also contributed to Saudi women's achievement of considerable personal and financial autonomy. This empowerment of Saudi women is expected to result in changes in roles, tasks, family, and social relationships. This will result in some problematic situations within the family and between husbands and wives. Since they are specialized in social work and represent the female segment, it was necessary to survey the female social work faculty. The selection of such a population provided an enhanced understanding of the issues and challenges faced by Saudi women.

The qualifying challenges that social work faces pertaining to women:

Qualifying challenges in social work consist of not just keeping pace with the curriculum and with the course of contemporary societal changes. It requires the monitoring of these aspects as well: the low level of field and scientific training for students of social work, the imbalance in the scientific and theoretical aspects, and the subsequent lowering of the level of graduates in the specialization of social work. In addition to the weakness of students' academic education programs and the lack of professional intervention skills and methods in accordance with contemporary social issues, there is poor supervision of field training for student social workers. All of these issues affect the outcomes of the social work specialization and thus, present a challenge in social work practice.

In the context of seeking the development of the professional practice of family social work, many studies have addressed the difficulties faced by family counsellors. Challenges pertaining to qualifying have received considerable attention since qualifying is the basis for the practice of family social work. In this regard, the results of several studies have identified the qualifying challenges facing staff in family counselling. Perhaps the most prominent of these are scientific and academic qualifications. Many studies indicate the weakness in practitioners' academic outcomes, as follows.

Pereira and Rekha (2017) indicates that the practical training received by practitioners was inadequate and the exposure to actual counselling conditions was insufficient during postgraduate studies. Smith, Moller, & Vossler (2017) showed that one of the most significant challenges facing the family counsellor was the creation of competencies required for practitioners working at this level. These are critical steps to building a coherent and evidence-based model for providing family counselling in primary care. Duggal, Sriram, & Jain (2018) also reported a lack of consistency in the counselling curriculum as well as a lack of qualifications to deal with the clients' concerns and anxiety.

Sweidan (2014) indicates that the gap between the academic study of specialists and field work in the family sphere is one of the most prominent qualifying barriers for family counsellors. Meanwhile, Noor (2014) indicates the need to provide competencies that are necessary for family counselling which include adequate knowledge, language, communication, attention, customs, and professional experience. The most significant challenges in the practice of family counselling are knowledge and skills whereas the results showed that the counsellors acknowledged that they lacked the education and training necessary to carry out family counselling. This is because it was provided as a training course and not as a regular aspect of study leading to extensive knowledge and good practice in this area.

Al-Semari (2016) indicates that one of the main challenges faced by family counselling practitioners is the gap between academic specialisation and professional requirements as well as the lack of family and marital counselling programs in academic institutions. There is also a shortage of specialized cadres in family and marital counselling.

From the above, it follows that previous studies that examined qualifying challenges almost unanimously agree that weaknesses in academic study and field training affect the quality of social work outcomes and the effectiveness of practice in the family sphere. This indicates the need to pay attention to scientific outcomes, reduce the gap between the academic and field aspects of training, and provide specialized courses in family social work that contain scientific, theoretical, and applied knowledge. It, in turn, contributes to refining the students of social work and help them keep pace with the current societal changes.

Professional challenges:

The challenges facing family counselling are tremendous. However, the practice of counselling by non-professionals is one of the main private problems and challenges marital and family counselling has to deal with. Amin and Bin Said (2014) indicated that more than 30% of the family counselling providers are non-professionals. This would affect the quality family counselling services, especially women, as they comprise the majority of counselling clients. In addition, females are believed to face more family problems because of the latest social, work, and legal changes in the country which might, in turn, yield more help seeking. So, there is a strong need for more regulations that restrict non-professionals from providing family counselling services.

Communities are undergoing many changes that result in complex and diverse family problems and due to this, workers at family counselling centres face many challenges related to professional practice and development. The incompetence of the staff at these centres is one of the most important challenges as they lack the knowledge and information related to family counselling. In this regard, Amin and Bin Said (2014) indicate that practitioners in family centres need a set of theoretical knowledge as part of their training, such as learning about family counselling strategies, marital therapy strategies, therapeutic theories, and models of intervention with the family. The same study indicates that the lack of knowledge, skills, theories, and modern therapeutic models are the most prominent challenges. The results of the study specify that even the workers believe that they need training to equip them with professional counselling skills for applying different therapeutic tactics.

The lack of family counselling courses for staff in family centres is one of the most important challenges facing practitioners. Al-Ashiwi (2018) indicates that 90% of their study sample expressed the need for a training program to develop their scientific and professional knowledge in the field of family counselling.

Duggal et al. (2018) also explains the need to develop family training, practice units, and practice legal consultancy to help counsellors understand and respond to couples' concerns and to guide their goals and interventions. The framework used should help to facilitate the characterisation and consolidation of concepts to achieve integration in various consultancy fields.

In this regard, Sweidan (2014) indicates that the trainers for the training courses are poorly selected and there is a shortage of specialists compared to the number of cases dealt with by the office.

Counselors face many professional challenges at the administrative and organizational level as well. Al-Saleh (2017) indicates that due to the low number of counsellors, counselling is limited to telephone

consultations only and the lack of provision of opportunities for counsellors to develop their expertise is one of the most important administrative challenges.

Pereira and Rekha (2017) also showed the effects of stress on counsellors due to the nature of their work; client problems lead to emotional exhaustion while low wages also cause stress. The results of this study also indicate that the absence of counselling service licenses by a government agency is a major disadvantage for Indian counsellors. Another professional challenge is the lack of spaces to carry out consultations, and therefore, the lack of confidentiality and privacy for clients. The results of the study also indicate that counsellors face the burden of clerical work which affects their time for consultancy and lack job security due to the nature of their contractual work.

Family burdens, in addition to professional burdens, are among the most important constraints to women's empowerment in the field of family counselling and guidance. Eckart and Daigle (2019) illustrated the impact of professional and family characteristics on women's work. The results of their study showed that working more than 40 hours a week, in addition to the family burden of caring for children under five and other people in need of care such as sick and elderly relatives, is extra pressure on the family counsellor. This increases the overlap between work and family commitments, causing exhaustion and thus, affecting their work with clients. Joseph and Nirmala (2019) also indicate that low wages, as well as the lack of occupational advantages and the need for on-the-job training, are among the main challenges faced by practitioners.

From the above, it follows that current societal changes require the development of professional practice skills for the counsellor and the provision of continuous training that is compatible with these changes to contribute to further professional development in this field.

Societal challenges:

The societal challenges facing women refer to the challenges pertaining to professional and ethical social work intervention since high numbers of family and marital consulting service providers are not specialized in social work or other assistive professions. Therefore, the client system, including women, would be affected by non-professional work. So, women exploitation, privacy, and the effectiveness of the consultation are all in jeopardy. This, in turn, would affect the society as a whole.

Due to the lack of transportation, household duties, and social stigma, women might drop consultations. Family counselling centres are already facing challenges in retaining clients, especially women, and continuing to serve them. So, in order to be more effective, family counselling centres need to have more flexible and operating hours and have other methods of providing services such as telephone counselling.

The societal challenges facing family social work in general are maintaining values, national identity, and family cohesion.

Many studies have aimed to identify and clarify the societal challenges or constraints facing practitioners in the family. First off, community awareness of counselling is low amongst the public: Pereira and Rekha (2017) indicate that people do not understand the difference between a counsellor, a clinical psychologist, and a psychiatrist.

Noor (2014) also indicated that future challenges include working with the family, noting the importance of cooperation and family participation in the process of counseling, financial problems, education, and the demographic background. Family awareness is one of the main challenges. Therefore, family awareness and involvement in the helping stage during the intervention process is one of the important challenges that social work is facing, particularly among female clients since women are more vulnerable and less supported by the family.

In this regard, Al-Saleh (2017) indicates the lack of community awareness of the importance of counselling, couples' refusal to talk about their problems or to attend the therapy sessions, in addition to the defensive attitude of the paterfamilias, which makes things difficult for the counsellors.

Darwish (2009) indicated that one of the most prominent challenges facing the social worker in the family area is the lack of understanding of the role of social workers in resolving family disputes as these differences are regarded as the family's internal affairs in which the social worker is not allowed to intervene. The researcher agrees with this finding that customs and traditions in the Saudi society consider family relations to be sacred, highly confidential and need not be discussed with non-family members, and this impedes the work of the social worker during their professional practice.

Healy and Meagher (2004) clarify that the lack of support for social work and the lack of recognition of its standing as a professional activity is one of the main challenges facing the social work profession. Healy and Meagher (2004) aimed to improve the professional requalifying of social work by addressing the challenge of the recognition of the profession. Their study revealed that despite the policy discourse focusing on the quality of social services, the practice environment is characterised by a lack of sufficient support for the social workers' work professionally. The study also examined the mechanisms for improving the recognition of social work as a professional activity by establishing professional associations and syndicates.

Sangar (2018) investigated the societal challenges that impede women's empowerment. The findings of

this study indicated unequal access to economic opportunities. This, in addition to inadequate safety measures and poor social security measures such as child custody and maternity benefits in the workplace, serves to impede women's equal participation in work.

In conclusion, practitioners in the field of family counselling face many challenges which impede or reduce professional practice. Given the complementarity of these areas and their impact on each other, there is a need for further study and research in this field.

Table 1. Centre the Caption above the Table

Variables		N	Mean
Group	1.	47	30.3
	2.	60	38.7
	3.	48	31.0
Age	18-21	150	96.8
	other	5	3.2
Gender	F	117	75.5
	M	38	24.5
Total		155	100

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Method

This is a descriptive study which uses a comprehensive survey as its methodology. The study population represents all the specialists in social work from the female teaching faculty in Saudi universities who teach social work.

Participants:

The study population consists of 72 female teaching staff members in Saudi universities.

Field of research:

This study was conducted with academic specialists in social work in Saudi universities as follows: Umm Al-Qura University, King Abdulaziz University, King Saud University, Imam Mohammed Bin Saud Islamic University, Imam Abdul Rahman Bin Faisal University, King Faisal University, Princess NouraBint Abdulrahman University, the University of Hail, and the University of Hafr Al Batin. The study was conducted one month after being approved by the Scientific Research Ethics Committee

Measurements:

For data collection, an Arabic point Likert scale was established and designed by the author after reviewing educational literature and previous studies related to the subject of the current study, (Amin & Bin Said, 2014; Rehfuss&Gambrell, 2014; AASWSW, 2015; Sanga, 2018; Duggal et al., 2018; Eckart& Daigle, 2019; Joseph & Nirmala, 2019). The scale consists of 54 statements divided into three aspects of focus: professional challenges (31 statements), qualifying challenges (13 statements), and societal challenges (10 statements). The survey contains axes:

First: the primary information (age, employment level, workplace, experiences in the academic field, professional experiences, years of work experience in the family field, chosen major).

Second: the survey contained of 45 sentences distributed in three axes: the major professional challenges (31 sentences), rehabilitation challenges (13 sentences), and societal challenges (10 sentences)

Third: to simplify the explanation of the results, it was explained by the five point Likert scale which provided every answer with a number:

Answer number	Strongly disagree	disagree	Agree in a medium level	agree	Strongly agree
	1	2	3	4	5

Data Collection:

An electronic questionnaire containing the three focuses of the study was designed with a statement declaring that "the data of this study are confidential and will only be used for scientific research purposes". The data were collected through distributing the link to this electronic questionnaire to all heads of the social work departments in the above-mentioned universities for distribution to the respondents. This method was used because of the

Variable #	Variables	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Percentage
20	Poor efficiency of family counselling and consultancy services introduced to clients	3.7500	.83	75.00
18	Lack of a family social work professional identity among other disciplines	3.7500	1.17185	75.00
14	Lack of an effective local ethical code for social workers in the field of family work	3.6944	1.27422	73.89
6	Poor case intervention skills for social workers working with families	3.6944	.88236	73.89
19	Lack of family counselling and family therapy services	3.6111	1.14517	72.22
5	Poor skills of social workers in working with families	3.5278	.99254	70.56
30	The stress of working with families impedes the specialist work with cases	3.4722	.87165	69.44
21	Insufficient time for family consultations	3.4722	.76861	69.44
23	A low number of specialized family clinics and centres in the field of working with families.	3.4444	1.17352	68.89
7	Lack of a clear system for evaluating the social worker's job in the field of working with families	3.2778	1.10342	65.56
26	Lack of appointments scheduling flexibility for clients by family centres.	3.2222	.89162	64.44
22	Lack of a "hotline" call service to solve family problems	3.0000	1.16280	60.00
Overall Professional Challenges		3.7903	.54230	75.81

As shown in Table 2, the statement with the highest mean score for agreement is "Lack of policies and legislation related to the regulation of the social work practice in the field of counselling and family therapy", with which 86.11% of the total respondents agreed. This response indicates that there is a fundamental and important challenge to the practice of family social work in the opinion of the respondents which expresses the need to focus on developing policies and legislation stemming from the problems and challenges of the current situation of social work practice in the field of counselling and family therapy. In particular, there should be punishments for anyone who practices family counselling without professional qualifications, especially on social media.

The sentence ranked second is "Long working hours in the field of working with families impedes the work of the specialist with cases" with which 85.56% of the total respondents agreed. This response indicates that long working hours impede domestic duties and participation in family activities. This leads to some family problems. The researcher attributes this finding to the stress facing professional practice, particularly in family counselling centres, leading to difficulties in achieving a balance between domestic and work responsibilities as the burdens and needs of the family are primarily women's responsibility. The culture of cooperation and participation between men and women in domestic work does not exist in the Saudi society; men believe that domestic responsibilities are a matter of concern for women only and this is consistent with the attitudes of Marxist feminism which considers women as primary products. Domestic work is always the responsibility of women and here, Marxist feminism confirms that women's departure from work is not enough to bring freedom as long as their work at home is a subject of privacy and a duty of women as they are still performing a dual role which requires double the effort.

Table 3. Table 3. the distribution of responses on the qualifying challenges.

Sentence #	Sentence	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	percentage
39	There is a gap between researchers and practitioners in the field of family counselling	4.2500	.68690	85.00
40	Lack of Arab social measures in the field of family counselling and therapy	4.0000	.91928	80.00
35	Low level of field and practical training for social work students in the field of family counselling	4.0000	1.21028	80.00
42	The language barrier prevents professional practice	3.9167	1.12275	78.33

Sentence #	Sentence	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	percentage
	from benefiting from the global knowledge production			
43	There is no national council for social work education	3.8611	.92395	77.22
37	The family curriculum is not included in the field training curriculum in social work	3.8611	1.25939	77.22
38	Low level of social work graduates in the field of family counselling	3.7778	1.03763	75.56
32	The social work curriculum and courses for family counselling are not adequately covered	3.7222	1.26960	74.44
36	There is poor supervision of the field training of students of specialist social work in the field of family counselling	3.6667	1.21028	73.33
41	Lack of diplomas specializing in family counselling and therapy	3.5278	1.12553	70.56
44	Lack of courses in the field of family work	3.4444	1.09915	68.89
33	The contents of the social work curriculum are not commensurate with the attitudes of the Kingdom's Vision 2030 in terms of family counselling and therapy	3.3333	1.30005	66.67
34	Poor focus on the curriculums of working with families	3.3056	1.31769	66.11
	Overall Qualifying Challenges	3.7436	.75303	74.87

From reviewing Table 3, it is clear that statement 39, "There is a gap between researchers and practitioners in the field of family counseling", is ranked first with an approval rate of 85%. This percentage indicates a gap between research and practice; a result that is not commensurate with the orientation of social work (evidence-based practice). Research and practice in social work are two sides of the same coin with the latter having a function in social work. The results of such research and studies must be applied and employed by practitioners in their profession. In contrast, practitioners themselves must conduct research that is commensurate with their practice problems.

The percentages of respondents who agreed with the rest of the sentences varied. In general, we conclude that the results of the analysis confirm the existence of many qualifying challenges facing social work in the field of counselling and family therapy, with an arithmetic mean of 3.74 and a standard deviation of 0.75, based on the opinions of the academics. The arithmetic means of the paragraphs relating to this focus ranged from 4.25 to 3.30.

Table4. Clarifies the distribution of responses to the societal challenges

Sentence #	Sentence	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Percentage
54	Media fails to define the role of the social worker and its response to family problems	4.1111	.97223	82.22
46	Lack of community awareness about the role of the social worker in working with families	3.9444	1.00546	78.89
49	Some clients believe that family disputes are an internal matter and the social worker is not allowed to intervene	3.7778	1.03763	75.56
45	Poor societal recognition of the social work profession in general and family social work in particular	3.6667	1.23334	73.34
51	Customers may withdraw from the field of working with families suddenly without completing therapy	3.6389	.95395	72.78
53	Customers in the field of working with families may use defensive tricks to "escape"	3.6389	.92395	72.78
52	Clients have no confidence in family social workers	3.5833	1.01745	71.67
50	Social customs prevent either spouse from transferring their disputes outside the family to seek solutions	3.5833	1.09737	67.22
47	There is a negative image of family counselling offices	3.3611	1.09165	61.11

48	There is a stigma associated with family counselling offices	3.0556	1.20899	60.00
	Overall societal challenges	3.0000	1.19187	72.72

Table 4 sets out the distribution of the study participants' responses to the statements representing the societal challenges facing social work in the field of family counselling and therapy in Saudi society. This table shows that the most approved sentence is "Media fails to define the role of the social worker and its response to family problems" with an agreement rate of 78.89%. This result is an indication that the various media should play a role in defining social work in the field of family counselling and therapy in Saudi society, clarifying its actual role and that there is an apparent lack of contribution from practitioners themselves in defining their role in this field, spreading awareness, conducting community initiatives, and covering them.

The statement ranked second is "Lack of community awareness about the role of the social worker in working with families" with which 78.89% of respondents agreed. This result is justified because of the multiple reasons mentioned previously with regard to the professional, qualifying and community challenges which lead to weakness in the role and identity of social work in the field of counselling and family therapy in the community. It is not limited to calls or counselling interviews based on preaching or stereotyping experiences in the form of the knowledge of practitioners who are not competent.

The sentence ranked third is "Some clients believe that family disputes are an internal matter and the social worker is not allowed to intervene" with an approval rate of 75.56%. This result is logical as family counselling spaces are a new prospect for the community members who are not used to disclosing the harm or deprivation they suffer and thus, might resort to extreme reservation which is a constraint to social workers' provision of appropriate services.

The percentage of agreement with the remaining statements varied. In general, we conclude that the results of the analysis confirm the existence of many societal challenges facing social work in the field of counselling and family therapy, with an overall arithmetic mean of 3.63, based on the opinions of academics. The arithmetic means of the statements within this focus ranged from 4.11 to 3.00.

Discussion:

The study revealed many challenges facing the practice of social work in the field of family counselling and therapy in Saudi society based on the opinions of academics specializing in social work.

1) Professional Challenges

The results of the study revealed that social workers in the field of counselling and family therapy face professional challenges. These challenges were represented in long working hours in the field of work with families which impede the specialists' work, the lack of specialization in some of the professional practices of social work in the field of working with families, and the lack of policies and legislation associated with organizing the practice of social work in the field of counselling and family therapy, amongst other challenges. The researcher attributes these findings to several factors, the most important of which is the poor recognition of the profession of social work in general and in the field of counselling and family therapy in particular which leads to interference between the many specialists working in this field. Bin Said and Amin and Bin Said (2014) also identified interference among specializations operating in social work centres that provide family counselling services, such as social work, psychology, and sociology. This result may also be due to the lack of practitioners in the social work profession who are qualified to work in the field of family counselling. This is confirmed by Al-Ashwi (2018) who concludes that social workers need many qualifications in the field of family counselling.

This finding is also consistent with those reported by Healy and Meagher (2004), confirming that there is an urgent need for professional qualification for social work and that there is insufficient support for the role of the social worker professionally. This was demonstrated by Duggal et al. (2018) who revealed that social workers working in the family field were not qualified to deal with certain cases.

2) Qualifying Challenges

The results of the study revealed that the practices of the social work profession in the field of family counselling and therapy face qualifying challenges. The most important of these challenges is the gap between research and practice in the field of family counselling and the low level of field and practical training for social work students in the field of family counselling. The researcher interprets this result to be a consequence of the poor coordination between the family centres and departments of social work in universities and the absence of joint projects between them. This is in addition to the fact that the majority of social work departments offer public programs to practice the profession of social work and the absence of a large number of specialized curriculums.

This finding is consistent with Darwish (2009) who revealed that social workers are facing severe qualifying challenges which prevent them from intervening in the family field such as inadequate in-service qualification through organizing courses that contribute to raising and developing performance. It also concurs with Amin and Bin Said (2014) who revealed that social workers working in family centres needed a set of theoretical

knowledge, such as identifying family counselling strategies, marital therapy strategies, therapeutic theories, and models of intervention with the family.

3) Societal Challenges

The results of this study revealed a set of societal challenges facing the practices of the social work profession in the field of family counselling and therapy. These findings may be associated with the previous results as it is logical that if social work practices in the field of family counselling and therapy are inadequate and some practitioners lack specialization, which affects the client's confidence in the practice, this prompts them to withdraw from the sessions suddenly without completing their therapy. This encourages the misconception that family disputes are an internal matter in which social workers should not intervene. The profession of family counsellor or therapist has not been given its rightful position among other professions by defining it for young children at primary educational levels.

This result can also be interpreted based on the entrenchment of customs and traditions in Saudi society which considers family relations sacred and highly confidential and does not allow them to be discussed, thus, impeding the work of social workers during their professional practice. This finding is consistent with the results of Darwish (2009) who revealed that one of the most important challenges facing the social worker in the family field is the lack of understanding of the role of social workers in resolving family disputes which are regarded as internal family issues on which the social worker has no right to intervene. It also concurs with the findings of Healy and Meagher (2004) who revealed that one of the greatest challenges facing social work is that of the recognition of the profession which can be addressed through media and the formation of professional associations.

Limitations of the present study:

This study has some limitations that should be noted such as the type of sample as it focused only on specialized academics. Despite these restrictions, the study recruited all the female teaching staff members (72) specializing in social work in Saudi Arabia.

Practice recommendations:

The results of this study indicate many recommendations for practicing social work in the field of family counselling and therapy to meet the challenges faced by practitioners in their work by improving the working conditions of practitioners in general and professional practices in particular, in addition to addressing the issue of working hours. It also recommends inviting university social work departments to establish partnerships and programs with centres that provide social services within the Saudi society. Moreover, the Ministry of Human Resources and Social Development should allocate an electronic family consultancy service that includes specialists in the field of family therapy guidance. This is similar to the project of the qualification portfolio for future spouses in which a group of specialists organized and participated in efforts in that field, achieving great success. This will contribute to improving the level of family counselling and therapy in the community and in building confidence.

Conclusion

The current study concludes that there are many challenges and obstacles (professional, qualifying, and community) facing social workers in the field of family counselling and therapy and it helps to understand those challenges and obstacles. Understanding and dealing with such challenges is the basis for acquiring comprehensive knowledge that ensures the success and effectiveness of the counselling process to help individuals and their families to achieve stability, compatibility, and adaptation.

Recommendations

This study is one of the few studies in the Saudi society to address the challenges facing the practice of social work in the field of family counselling and therapy based on the opinions of specialists in social work. Accordingly, future research must focus on finding solutions to the difficulties and constraints faced by the practice of social work in general and family counselling and therapy in particular. These studies must introduce recommendations that can feasibly be implemented in this field. Research involving a wide range of social workers working in various fields of social work would yield more realistic results.

Ethics:

Ethical approval for this research was provided by the Standing Committee for Scientific Research Ethics and the Subcommittee on Human and Social Research Ethics at KSU in Riyadh, KSA. The participation of the respondents was optional and it was explained to them that the data they provided would be confidential, the information would be used only for scientific research purposes, and that no information would be mentioned that would reveal the identities of the teaching staff involved in the study.

Funding:

The researcher did not receive any financial support for the study or for the publication of this article.

Acknowledgments:

I acknowledge and appreciate all academics specialized in social work departments in Saudi Arabia for giving this research their precious time and sharing their information.

Researcher's website: <https://faculty.ksu.edu.sa/kalabdulkreem>

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Author Information

Khaloud Barjas Alabdulkareem

King Saud University

Assistant Professor, Department of Social Studies, King Saud University, Saudi Arabia, Riyadh
